

Supplemental Material

Shell trace elemental fingerprints of the deep-sea methane seep mussel *Gigantidas childressi* vary by depth, site, and growth region

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1 Methods

1.1 Data reduction

MATLAB software (peakid_program.m) was used to identify signal peaks as points greater than three standard deviations above the mean of the background; this program output Excel spreadsheets corresponding to “no peak” and “peak” signal per sample. MATLAB software was then used to produce a laser log, which contains timing information about laser-on and laser-off intervals and is read by LA-ICP-MS data reduction software IOLITE (Version 4) (Paton et al., 2011). The same MATLAB program was used to trim the tail of the peak of each sample to exclude the onset of washout decay and to exclude shell transition zones between shell growth regions that could confound differences in TEFs among samples. Peak tails were

trimmed by identifying where signal intensity reduced by one magnitude and subtracting 0.6 seconds of laser-on time from that value. Some oddly formatted samples were manually processed, including standard reference materials. Raw data files contain the start and end times (laser-on and laser-off times) for each sample.

Data reduction was performed in IOLITE, including peak integration and background removal (using blanks as a baseline) according to the Trace Elements Data Reduction Scheme (DRS) applied to the two analytical sessions (days of instrument operation), separately (i.e., Oct. 18th and Oct. 19th). The DRS calibrated values based on standard reference materials NIST 612 and NIST 614, and NIST 616 was used as a consistency standard to calculate precision— % residual standard deviation (% RSD; standard deviation * 100 / mean; see below). Ca⁴⁸ was used as the internal standard. Iolite used formulas for sensitivity and calibration following Longerich et al. (1996), which normalized signal to volume of sample ablated per sample. Because the volume of sample ablated is a consequence of ionization efficiency and sample introduction parameters, such normalization improves comparability among studies that may use somewhat different methods for sample preparation and measurement.

Measured values of NIST 612 and NIST 614 were checked against accepted values to calculate recovery. Accepted values were sourced from GeoReM Preferred Values (Jochum et al., 2005), which contains published analytical data and compilation values, including uncertainty and metadata. GeoReM Preferred Values have become consensus values, and improve over time as more data is compiled from labs globally. Preferred Values are very commonly used for this purpose and NIST 612 is particularly well-characterized by GeoReM sources, including for Mg and Co, which are not NIST-certified. Recoveries were low (ideal) for NIST 612 for elements

ultimately used in statistical analyses: $\text{Mg}^{26} = -0.76\%$ and 0.09% ; $\text{Sr}^{88} = 1.55\%$ and -0.08% ; and $\text{Ba}^{138} = 2.46\%$ and -0.08% for the first and second analytical sessions, respectively.

Similarly, the proportion of measurements above levels of detection (LOD) were high, and % RSD was low ($< 15\%$) for these elements: $\text{Mg}^{26} = 100\%$ of samples above LOD, mean % RSD = 10.57; $\text{Sr}^{88} = 90\%$ of samples above LOD, mean % RSD = 10.76; $\text{Ba}^{138} = 100\%$ of samples above LOD, mean % RSD = 10.77. Samples with measurements below LOD were removed. Between-sample % RSD was calculated and compared to consistency standard % RSD to verify that differences between samples were larger than the error. The mean detection limits for the first, more conservative analytical session, were: $0.28 \text{ mmol mol}^{-1}$ (Mg:Ca), $0.005 \text{ mmol mol}^{-1}$ (Cr:Ca), $0.003 \text{ mmol mol}^{-1}$ (Mn:Ca), $5.98 \text{ mmol mol}^{-1}$ (Fe:Ca), $0.04 \text{ mmol mol}^{-1}$ (Co:Ca), $0.004 \text{ mmol mol}^{-1}$ (Ni:Ca), $0.001 \text{ mmol mol}^{-1}$ (Cu:Ca), $0.003 \text{ mmol mol}^{-1}$ (Sr:Ca), $0.06 \text{ mmol mol}^{-1}$ (Cd:Ca), $< 0.001 \text{ mmol mol}^{-1}$ (Ba:Ca), $< 0.001 \text{ mmol mol}^{-1}$ (Sn:Ca), and $< 0.001 \text{ mmol mol}^{-1}$ (Pb:Ca). Table 2 summarizes quality assurance and precision metrics for all elements. Critically, these metrics were determined only after removing samples that may have been subject to laser shoot-through (i.e., excessive destruction during data collection due to shell weakness).

MATLAB software (driftchecker_dryad.mlx) was used to evaluate machine (measurement) drift by the spectrometer by i) creating a scatter plot of data in units of ppm, ii) fitting a linear trendline for each analytical session (Oct. 18th and Oct. 19th), iii) calculating the mean signal for a given analytical session, and iv) expressing the slope of the trendline as a proportion (percentage) of the mean signal for each analytical session. The program output a dimensionless ratio that represented how steep the trendline for each element was relative to the mean signal, which was used as a measure of the severity of machine drift. Measurements for

analytes ultimately used in statistical analyses were determined to have not drifted: Mg²⁶ = 0.08% and 0.56%; Sr⁸⁸ = 0.02% and 0.35%; Ba¹³⁸ = 0.29% and 1.04%; Cd¹¹¹ = 0.54% and 1.7%; Sn¹¹⁸ = 0.46% and 0.78% for the first and second analytical sessions, respectively (Supplemental Table 1).

MATLAB software (mmolconverter_mk2_dryad.mlx) was used to convert IOLITE- output data in units of ppm to units of mmol:mol X:Ca (whole element:internal standard) ratios. Because this conversion step requires a known or assumed value for the calcium concentration in the sample, and because we are not aware of known values for *G. childressi* (e.g., measured with ICP-OES), we assumed a calcium concentration of 400,432 ppm (40.0432 wt % Ca) in samples. That is, samples were assumed to be 100% stoichiometrically pure CaCO₃ which is the concentration of calcium in stoichiometrically pure calcium carbonate as calculated using published atomic weights (NIST Standard Reference Database Number 69; <https://webbook.nist.gov/chemistry/>). While this value is not necessarily the true concentration of Ca in our samples, by providing this scalar value we improve comparability of our results among studies that may use different values. The datasets for both analytical sessions were combined at this stage.

During preliminary visualization of potential outliers using *n*MDS plots, we observed that samples appeared to be split into two separate groups that were not clearly associated with differences among levels of any study factor (Supplemental Fig. 1); that is, levels of each methodological and study factor existed in both arbitrary groups of samples. Although no factor appeared to explain the grouping, Mg:Ca and Sr:Ca did appear to be responsible for separating the groups (Supplemental Fig. 1). Such grouping had the potential to confound tests of study factors by potentially capturing variation associated with the unidentified but apparently

influential factor(s). This was addressed by generating two datasets: 1) “Inclusive”, which included Mg:Ca, Sr:Ca, and Ba:Ca ratios and retained the aforementioned grouping, and 2) “Exclusive”, which replaced Mg:Ca and Sr:Ca with two other elements— Cd:Ca and Sn:Ca— and dissolved the grouping. Both datasets were analyzed and results interpreted separately. However, we discuss only results for Inclusive data. This is because links between temperature and Mg:Ca and Sr:Ca ratios in bivalves are well-established (Dodd 1965; Mouchi et al., 2013; Kroll et al., 2016; Durham et al., 2017; Zhao et al., 2017; Carvalho et al., 2019), and therefore Mg:Ca and Sr:Ca ratios are likely very informative compared to other elemental ratios. The Ba:Ca ratio remained in both datasets because it may be associated with surface-derived carbon from phytoplankton blooms (Vander Putten et al., 2000; Thébault et al., 2009; Fröhlich et al., 2022) and/or methane seepage rate (Ke et al., 2024) and Ba-rich methane emissions (Torres et al., 2001; Wang et al., 2022).

Outliers were removed from both Inclusive and Exclusive datasets in three phases:

- (i) elements except Mg, Sr, Ba, and Sn (for the Inclusive dataset) or Cd, Sn, and Ba (for the Exclusive dataset) were removed due to poor QA/QC metrics. Samples below LOD were not considered. Analytical sessions were individually inspected and samples with Sn (tin) values above three standard deviations plus the mean were identified as potential instances of laser shoot-through and consequent tape ablation
- (ii) Samples identified by step (i) were removed. Days were individually inspected and samples with elemental values greater than five standard deviations plus the mean were identified as outliers and flagged for removal
- (iii) Samples identified by step (ii) were removed. Finally, samples with any elemental value below LOD were removed and the two analytical sessions were combined.

After identification and removal of outliers and samples with values below LOD, we proceeded with statistical analysis on both the Inclusive and Exclusive datasets.

1.2 Iterative development of omnibus PERMANOVA model

A highly statistically robust, optimized Type I SS PERMANOVA model was developed by starting with a very simple model and iteratively increasing model complexity while removing irrelevant terms. Specifically, consecutive models :

1. Tested all terms except depth and complex interactions (model 1a).
2. Iterated the continuous covariate burn number variable to determine the robustness of methods to the position of the covariate (models 1b – 1d).
3. Removed consistently highly insignificant terms that were above a removal threshold ($p \geq 0.25$) and complex (3-way or greater) interaction terms unless associated with hypotheses, as well as terms for which there were insufficient degrees of freedom to use for comparisons (model 1e).
4. Added the continuous covariate depth, the interaction between geographic region and depth, and mussel growth region contrasts (model 2).
5. Removed the interaction between geographic region and depth, and iterated depth to determine robustness of study factors to the position of the covariate (models 3-4)
6. Repeated step (3) to produce a final, highly statistically robust model.

Because the term for depth somewhat correlated with the order of ablation (burn number; $R^2=0.28$) and tray loadings (sequence; $R^2=0.31$) (Supplemental Fig. 2), PERMANOVA controlled for these effects prior to testing study factors (i.e., depth, geographic region, etc.).

1.3 Null hypothesis rejection criteria

Null hypotheses were rejected if either PERMANOVA or CAP results for either the growth region aggregated dataset or one or more growth region controlled (GRC) data subsets were significant. Critically, the growth region aggregated dataset had a higher sample size than GRC subsets, which improved statistical power but may have confounded dispersing and settled shell trends. Conversely, GRC subsets had lower sample sizes, poorer sample distribution, and reduced statistical power, yet controlled for specific growth regions (i.e., hypothetically different population pools and settlement environmental conditions). Therefore, when differences in TEFs are reliably observed in the dataset with the best sample size and distribution (aggregated data), less statistically powerful analyses of growth region controlled (GRC) subsets may help infer ecological cause (i.e., whether differences may be associated with dispersal strategies or environmental conditions). The PERMDISP and CAP leave-one-out protocols were not conducted on *a posteriori* data subsets since these were characterized by lower sample sizes and poorer distribution than the original growth region-aggregated dataset. Therefore, results for *a posteriori* tests are fairly liberal.

1.4 PERMANOVA validation with PERMDISP

Because PERMANOVA can confound differences in the mean (centroid) location of groups with differences in dispersion of points within groups in multivariate datasets, and can report statistical significance despite potentially high within-group dispersion, post-hoc permutational dispersion tests (PERMDISP) were conducted for any significant categorical PERMANOVA explanatory variables (i.e., except the continuous covariate depth). PERMDISP tested if point dispersion within each group's data from their centroid may have influenced PERMANOVA significance. If PERMDISP was significant then within-group dispersion may

have influenced PERMANOVA significance. In these cases, PERMANOVA reliability was assessed for each term by 1) visually inspecting *m*MDS plots for clear separation between groups and 2) evaluating whether the test was conservative or liberal according to whether groups with larger or smaller sample sizes possessed greater dispersion, respectively, per PERMANOVA guidelines (Anderson et al., 2013). Dispersion within levels of an explanatory variable was evaluated by PERMDISPs conducted on resemblance matrices of distances among centroids (DAC) of lower-order terms to control for dispersion belonging to lower-order terms, although we also report results for PERMDISPs conducted on the original resemblance matrix.

2 Discussion of settler shell results for Inclusive data

2.1 Differences in TEFs among depths (settler shell)

TEFs differed significantly among depths based only on CAP, not PERMANOVA, possibly due to very subtle differences in TEFs among depths. Because barium is traditionally associated with phytoplankton blooms and consequent increases in particulate Ba in seawater, as for *Mytilus edulis* (Vander Putten et al., 2000), and because settler shell from shallower depths had larger Ba:Ca ratios than those from deeper depths, results may reflect a decrease in surface-derived nutrition (e.g., Ba-rich phytoplankton) with increasing depth. Alternatively, Ba:Ca ratios could be linked with Ba-rich methane emissions as for *Gigantidas haimaensis* (Wang et al., 2022) and Vesicomylid clams (Torres et al., 2001) or could reflect a combined influence of POM ingestion and methane seepage rate (e.g., Ke et al., 2024) that varies with depth.

More commonly used as temperature proxies are Mg:Ca ratios (Dodd 1965; Mouchi et al., 2013; Durham et al., 2017) and Sr:Ca ratios (Kroll et al., 2016; Zhao et al., 2017; Carvalho et al., 2019), including those for *Gigantidas platifrons* and *G. haimaensis* from cold seeps in the

South China Sea (Cai et al., 2025), yet our results indicate little correlate between these ratios and depth for settler shell. Therefore, it seems most reasonable to speculate that Ba:Ca ratios for settler shell reflect gradients in nutrition or different nutritional sources among depths.

As previously mentioned, vital effects such as shell growth rate, ontogenetic age, and metabolism could influence shell TEFs, particularly Sr:Ca ratios (Gillikin et al., 2005; Schöne et al., 2011; Immenhauser et al., 2016), and these could obscure or confound relationships with environmental factors. If this is the case for *Gigantidas childressi*, results imply that vital effects or the combined influence of vital effects and temperature do not differ linearly among depths with respect to settler shell, although these effects could still vary significantly but non-linearly. For example, growth rate or metabolism may not linearly decline with depth, but may still significantly vary non-linearly. Alternatively, such effects may be fairly homogeneous among depths.

2.2 Differences in TEFs between geographic regions or sampling years (settler shell)

As previously stated, the GOM and WAM were sampled in May and June 2014 and July 2015, respectively, which precludes determination of real differences in TEFs among geographic regions versus sampling years. Differences in TEFs between geographic regions were detected only in growth region-aggregated data and settler D shells, and only using CAP, not PERMANOVA. TEFs may differ among geographic regions due to predominant ocean currents or geology in both regions or differences in methane flux or carbon sources, which may also influence vital effects. Ultimately, interpretation of differences in TEFs among geographic regions should be viewed as very tentative due to the confoundment with sampling year and very small effect size.

Only Ba:Ca ratios strongly correlated with separation among geographic regions, and Ba:Ca ratios were generally larger for samples from the GOM. This may be because the GOM and WAM differ geologically; many sites on the WAM do not possess hydrocarbon basins whereas many GOM sites do (McVeigh et al., 2018). Thus, sulfate reduction at WAM seeps is driven by anaerobic oxidation of methane whereas it is driven by oxidation of organic matter such as hydrocarbons and oil at GOM seeps (Joye et al., 2004). Perhaps these overarching geologic differences between geographic regions influence geographic region-specific settler shell TEFs that are far weaker than differences in settler shell TEFs among individual sites and depths. Mussel condition or other vital effects could also vary among geographic regions due to regional geology.

Because samples were collected in different years, differences in settler shell TEFs among geographic regions may also reflect temporal variability of field-wide methane seep environmental conditions. For instance, seep reservoir pressure can wax and wane at seasonal to multidecadal timescales (Leifer 2023), and whole seep fields may become depressurized, deplete, open, or close (Bradley et al., 2010) or explosively vent over time (Darnell and Flemings, 2015), which could influence shell elemental uptake in one geographic region versus another, independent of regional geology. In fact, our observation that Ba:Ca strongly discriminated among geographic regions may reflect the influence of differential methane flux on Ba:Ca ratios, as identified for Vesicomid clams from seeps on the Cascadia Margin (Torres et al., 2001) and *Gigantidas spp.* from Haima cold seeps (Wang et al., 2022). Alternatively, reliance of *G. childressi* on phytodetritus, which may influence Ba:Ca uptake as for *Mytilus edulis* (Vander Putten et al., 2000), may differ among geographic regions, with *G. childressi* on the WAM being more reliant on phytodetritus than those in the GOM (Demopoulos et al., 2019).

3 Discussion of differences in TEFs between geographic regions (growth region-aggregated Inclusive data)

With respect to shell growth region-aggregated data analyzed by CAP, Sr:Ca and Mg:Ca correlated strongly with differences in TEFs among geographic regions, with larger Sr:Ca ratios and smaller Mg:Ca ratios for GOM samples. Interpretation of this result from a larval shell perspective requires the assumption that the data were not overly influenced by differences in TEFs among geographic regions for settler D shell. If this assumption is met, the result would suggest that larvae use different dispersal strategies or that different proportions of larval pools use the same strategies in the GOM as in the WAM. This could be caused by the Loop Current or Gulf Stream skewing dispersal potential or favoring certain dispersal strategies in the regions. However, this interpretation is not firm for two reasons. First, significant differences in TEFs among geographic regions for settler shell may have influenced the significance for growth region-aggregated data as identified with CAP. Second, PERMANOVA did not detect significant differences in TEFs among geographic regions for growth region-aggregated or growth region-controlled data, Therefore, significant differences in TEFs among geographic regions may be primarily but very weakly driven by settler shell TEFs.

4 Discussion of Inclusive data interaction results

4.1 Interaction between geographic region and growth region

We observed no significant interaction between geographic region and mussel growth region according to the overall PERMANOVA test, including when only considering differences among prodissoconch shell and differences between prodissoconch and dissoconch shell. These results suggest that the two geographic regions are not more easily distinguishable from each

other for a given growth region. This result is somewhat contradictory to our finding that geographic region was discriminable according to CAP analysis of the settled D shell data subset, though the implications of these results are similar: the effect of geographic region is very weak, and the effect of the interaction of geographic region and growth region is not possible to observe with PERMANOVA.

4.2 Interaction between site and growth region

There was a significant interaction between site within geographic region and growth region when only considering differences among prodissoconch shell and, separately, differences between prodissoconch and dissoconch shell. These results suggest that differences in TEFs among prodissoconch and dissoconch growth regions exist between different sites in the same geographic region. This compliments our observation of significant differences between sites such that different population pools may exist and contribute to certain sites (according to prodissoconch results) or that site conditions vary (according to dissoconch results).

5 Results for Exclusive data

The results for Inclusive data are provided in the main body of the text. This section describes the results for Exclusive data, which replaced Mg:Ca and Sr:Ca elemental ratios with Cd:Ca and Sn:Ca elemental ratios, respectively. Ba:Ca ratios were included in both Inclusive and Exclusive datasets so that these datasets were not completely different from one another. About 50% of Exclusive data samples were discarded to permit Cd:Ca and Sn:Ca elemental ratios to be used due to these elemental ratios being below level of detection for many samples.

Hypothesis 1: TEFs do not significantly change sequentially along the continuous depth gradient when accounting for methods factors such as burn number (ablation order), burn date, sequence, or burn group, and excluding other influences such as geographic region, site, individual variability (sample number), and shell growth region

For growth region-aggregated data, TEFs did not differ significantly along a continuous depth gradient (650 m to 2,200 m) based on PERMANOVA (Supplemental Table 4) and explained 9.28% of the variation in the data. TEFs did vary significantly along the depth gradient based on CAP (Supplemental Table 5), and the canonical axis explained 28.17% of variation in the data (Supplemental Fig. 3; Supplemental Table 5). The canonical axis correlated most strongly with Ba:Ca ($r=+0.93$) (Supplemental Table 7). Leave-one-out allocation success (%) was not calculated for depth.

For growth region-controlled data subsets, TEFs did not vary significant with depth based on PERMANOVA (Supplemental Table 4) but did vary significantly for each growth region based on CAP (Supplemental Fig. 4; Supplemental Table 5). The first canonical axis explained 30%, 36%, and 38% of variation in the data for PD1, PD2, and D-shell growth regions, respectively (Supplemental Table 5), which correlated most strongly with Ba:Ca ratios for PD1 ($r=+0.95$) and D-shell ($r=+0.96$), and Sn:Ca for PD2 ($r=-0.60$) (Supplemental Table 7).

Hypothesis 2: TEFs are not significantly different between geographic regions (GOM and WAM) when treated as a fixed factor after accounting for methods factors and depth, and excluding other influences such as site, individual variability (sample number), and shell growth region

For growth region-aggregated data, TEFs did not vary significantly among geographic regions based on PERMANOVA (Supplemental Table 4) but did based on CAP analyses

(Supplemental Table 5), and the canonical axis explained 12% of variation in the data (Supplemental Fig. 5; Supplemental Table 5), which most strongly correlated with Ba:Ca ($r=+0.63$) (Supplemental Table 7). Mean leave-one-out allocation success was 66%, with 67% of samples successfully allocated to the GOM and 60% to the WAM (Supplemental Table 8).

For growth region-controlled data, TEFs did not significantly differ among geographic regions for any shell growth region based on PERMANOVA (Supplemental Table 4) but did for PD2 and D-shell based on CAP, for which the first canonical axis explained 15% and 22% of the variation in the data, respectively (Supplemental Fig. 7; Supplemental Table 5). The first canonical axis most strongly correlated with Sn:Ca ($r=+0.83$) for PD1 and PD2 ($r=-0.77$), and Cd:Ca for D-shell ($r=+0.76$) (Supplemental Table 7). Overall, the GOM had larger ratios of Cd:Ca and Ba:Ca and smaller ratios of Sn:Ca than the WAM (Supplemental Fig. 6).

Hypothesis 3: TEFs are not significantly different between sites within geographic regions when site is treated as a random factor after accounting for methods factors, depth, and geographic region

For growth region-aggregated data, TEFs did not differ significantly among sites based on PERMANOVA (Supplemental Table 4) nor CAP (Supplemental Fig. 8; Supplemental Table 5). PERMDISP analysis conducted on the resemblance matrix of the sample number distances among centroids matrix was not significant (Supplemental Table 9); therefore, the PERMANOVA test was conservative. Based on PERMANOVA, the site term explained 25% of variation in the data (Supplemental Table 6). Based on CAP, the canonical axis explained 51% of the variation in the data (Supplemental Fig. 8; Supplemental Table 5). The first canonical axis most strongly correlated with Ba:Ca ratios ($r=0.87$) (Supplemental Table 7). Mean leave-one-out

allocation success was 42% with the highest values being for Brine Pool (72%) and Norfolk Canyon (50%) (Supplemental Table 8).

With respect to growth region-controlled data, TEFs differed significantly among sites only for PD2 shell based on PERMANOVA (Supplemental Table 4) and for each growth region based on CAP (Supplemental Fig. 9; Supplemental Table 5). The first canonical axis explained 49%, 71%, and 54% of the variation in the data for PD1, PD2, and D-shell growth regions, respectively (Supplemental Table 5), which strongly correlated with Ba:Ca for PD1 ($r=0.92$), PD2 ($r=0.86$), and D-shell ($r=0.98$) (Supplemental Table 7). Elemental ratios varied considerably among sites with no clear pattern across all sites except for Ba:Ca, which appeared to shrink if sites were ordered by depth (Supplemental Fig. 6).

Hypothesis 4: TEFs are not significantly different between growth regions (PD1, PD2, and D) when treated as a fixed factor and after accounting for methods factors, depth, geographic region, site, and individual variability (sample number) as a random factor

TEFs did not significantly differ among shell growth regions based on PERMANOVA (Supplemental Table 4) nor CAP analyses (Supplemental Table 5). The growth region term explained 7% of the variability in the data based on PERMANOVA (Supplemental Table 6). The first canonical axis explained 3% of variation in the data cloud (Supplemental Table 5), which most strongly correlated with Ba:Ca ($r=0.98$) (Supplemental Table 7). Mean leave-one-out allocation success was 38%, and settled D-shell was allocated most successfully (55%), followed by PD2 shell (38%) and PD1 shell (18%) (Supplemental Table 8). Overall, no clear pattern in elemental ratios were observed among growth regions (Supplemental Fig. 6).

Hypothesis 4a: Differences in TEFs between prodissoconch and dissoconch shell growth regions are insignificant; note that there are insufficient degrees of freedom to test differences among only prodissoconch regions

TEFs did not vary significantly between prodissoconch and dissoconch shell growth regions based on PERMANOVA analyses (Supplemental Table 4). The difference in TEFs between levels of these groups explained 6.7% of variation in the data (Supplemental Table 6).

Hypothesis 5: The effect of growth region does not vary significantly by geographic region, or vice-versa

TEFs did vary significantly among different growth regions across geographic regions, or vice-versa, based on PERMANOVA analysis (Supplemental Table 4). This interaction explained 37% of variation in the data (Supplemental Table 6).

Hypothesis 5a: Differences in TEFs among prodissoconch growth regions do not vary significantly across geographic regions, or vice-versa

TEFs did not vary significantly among prodissoconch growth regions across geographic regions, or vice-versa, based on PERMANOVA analysis (Supplemental Table 4). This contrast explained 39% of variation in the data (Supplemental Table 6).

Hypothesis 5b: Differences in TEFs between prodissoconch and dissoconch growth regions do not vary significantly across geographic regions, or vice-versa

TEFs did not vary significantly between prodissoconch and dissoconch growth regions across geographic regions, or vice-versa, based on PERMANOVA analysis (Supplemental Table 4). This contrast explained 23% of variation in the data (Supplemental Table 6).

Hypothesis 6: The effect of growth region does not vary significantly across different sites within a given geographic region, or vice-versa

TEFs did vary significantly among different among growth regions across different sites within geographic regions, or vice-versa, based on PERMANOVA analysis (Supplemental Table 4). This interaction explained 24% of variation in the data (Supplemental Table 6).

Hypothesis 6a: Differences in TEFs among prodissoconch growth regions do not vary significantly across different sites within the same geographic region, or vice-versa

TEFs did vary significantly among different prodissoconch growth regions (PD1 and PD2) across sites within geographic regions, or vice-versa, based on PERMANOVA analysis (Supplemental Table 4). This contrast explained 33% of variation in the data (Supplemental Table 6).

Hypothesis 6b: Differences in TEFs between prodissoconch and dissoconch growth regions do not vary significantly across different sites within the same geographic region, or vice-versa

TEFs did vary significantly among prodissoconch and dissoconch growth regions across different sites within geographic regions, or vice-versa, based on PERMANOVA analysis (Supplemental Table 4). This contrast explained 16% of variation in the data (Supplemental Table 6).

5.1 Effect size and mean leave-one-out allocation success for Exclusive data

PERMANOVA-derived effect size of the main effects for Exclusive data was highest for site (25.42%), followed by depth (9.28%) and growth region (7.10%) (Supplemental Table 6).

The CAP-derived canonical axis, or the combination of PC axes that maximized distances among samples (CAP 1) score was highest for site (51%), followed by depth (28%) and geographic region (12%), with growth region having a minimal score (3%) (Supplemental Table 8).

Classification success for geographic region was relatively high (66%), though was relatively low for site (43%) and growth region (38%) (Supplemental Table 8).

6 Supplemental Tables

Supplemental Table 1. Estimation of analyte signal drift for both analytical sessions. Drift was considered to have occurred if the slope of the linear line-of-best-fit equation for the mean counts per second (CPS) signal was more than 3% for a given analyte. * = analyte used in statistical analyses of Inclusive or Exclusive data.

Analyte	Linear best-fit equation slope as % of mean CPS signal		Drift observed (Y/N; slope % > 3)
	Sess. 1	Sess. 2	
Mg26*	0.08	0.56	N
Ca48	0.12	0.1	N
Cr52	0.87	0.4	N
Mn55	0.49	0.82	N
Fe57	1.16	1.74	N
Co59	0.05	1	N
Ni60	0.1	2.44	N
Cu63	0.92	7.26	Y, during session 2
Sr88*	0.02	0.35	N
Cd111*	0.54	1.7	N
Ba138*	0.29	1.04	N
Sn118*	0.46	0.78	N
Pb208	0.85	5.57	Y, during session 2

Supplemental Table 2. Classification success of cross-validation of *Gigantidas childressi* Inclusive data. (A) two geographic regions (GOM and WAM), (B) eight sites (Brine Pool – BP, GB907, GB648, Veatch Canyon – VEC, New England Canyon – NE, Norfolk Canyon – NC, Mississippi Canyon 853 – MC853, Alaminos Canyon 645 – AC645), and (C) three growth regions (prodissoconch I – PD1, prodissoconch II – PD2, dissoconch – D).

(A) Geographic region

Orig group	Classified group		Group N	% Correct
	GOM	WAM		
GOM	123	47	170	72.353
WAM	27	21	48	43.75
Total Correct: 144/218 (66.055%)				
Total Incorrect: 74/218 (33.945%)				

(B) Site

Orig group	Classified group								Group N	% Correct
	BP	GB907	GB648	VEC	NE	NC	MC853	AC645		
BP	30	1	2	0	0	1	4	3	41	73.171
GB907	6	3	4	7	1	9	12	8	50	6
GB648	1	6	8	4	1	3	8	13	44	18.182
VEC	1	0	1	6	0	0	0	5	13	46.154
NE	0	2	2	3	0	2	2	4	15	0
NC	0	1	0	9	2	2	2	4	20	10
MC853	8	2	1	4	1	0	6	4	26	23.077
AC645	0	0	1	0	0	5	0	3	9	33.333
Total Correct: 58/218 (26.606%)										
Total Incorrect: 160/218 (73.394%)										

(C) Growth region

Orig group	Classified group			Group N	% Correct
	PD1	PD2	D		
PD1	15	37	8	60	25
PD2	6	68	8	82	82.927
D	1	25	50	76	65.789
Total Correct: 133/218 (61.009%)					
Total Incorrect: 85/218 (38.991%)					

Supplemental Table 3. Permutational dispersion (PERMDISP) test on *Gigantidas childressi*

Inclusive data. PERMDISP tested if within-group dispersion could have influenced PERMANOVA significance. F = F value; df1 = first degrees of freedom value, attributed to variance between groups; df2 = second degrees of freedom value, attributed to variance within groups; P-perm = p-value under permutation; Lib/Con/Unc/Insig = identifier for if the test was liberal (smaller group(s) has greater dispersion), conservative (larger group(s) has greater dispersion), uncertain (high number of groups with different dispersions obscures clear patterns), or insignificant at the 5% significance level. Bold values indicate significance at the 5% significance level.

Source of variation	F	df1	df2	P-perm	Lib/Con/Unc/Insig
Site (on Sample Num DAC)	3.0235	7	84	0.0142	Liberal
Site (no DAC)	3.0076	7	210	0.1343	Insignificant
Sample Num	3.4356	91	126	0.3201	Insignificant
Growth Region	10.761	2	215	0.0001	Liberal

Supplemental Table 4. Multivariate permutational ANOVA analysis on Exclusive data showing the impact of ecological study factors on the elemental composition of larval and settled juvenile shells of *Gigantidas childressi*. (A) *A priori* analysis using growth region-aggregated data. (B) Post-hoc analysis using PD1 shell data. (C) Post-hoc analysis using PD2 shell data. (D) Post-hoc analysis using D-shell data. The Type I SS analysis first accounts for variability associated with methods (Burn date, Sequence, Burn group), then factors in descending ecological hierarchical order. Depth is prioritized before other ecological study factors. Italicized factors indicate contrasts within a study factor. Asterisks significant effects at the 5% significance level; for post-hoc data, significant effects at this level after adjustment for multiple comparisons. df = degrees of freedom; MS = mean sum of squares; Pseudo-F = F value by permutation; P-perm = p-value under permutation; Perm # = number of unique permutations (of 9,999).

(A) Source of variation (<i>a priori</i>)	df	MS	Pseudo-F	P-perm	Perm#
Sequence	2	13.956	1.8244	0.1567	9960
Depth	1	25.887	1.9027	0.2196	9960
Geographic reg	1	5.4386	0.61328	0.5778	9949
Site(Geographic reg)	3	11.95	3.6091	0.0013*	9941
Sample number(Site(Geographic reg))	55	3.1749	2.481	0.0001*	9829
Growth region	2	8.5287	1.7786	0.1607	9952
<i>Among prodissoconch</i>	1	7.796	1.2713	0.3248	9958
<i>Between prodissoconch and diss.</i>	1	9.254	2.0613	0.1653	9961
Geographic reg x Growth region	2	9.6079	3.1477	0.0469*	9961
<i>Geographic reg x Among prodissoconch</i>	1	9.6466	2.4492	0.1821	9961
<i>Geographic reg x Between pro. and diss.</i>	1	7.7478	2.628	0.135	9962
Site(Geographic region) x Growth region	9	3.8089	2.9764	0.0002*	9910
<i>Site(Geographic reg) x Among prodissoconch</i>	4	4.6947	4.3498	0.0026*	9936
<i>Site(Geographic reg) x Between pro. and diss.</i>	5	3.5324	2.1201	0.0332*	9922
Residuals	67	1.2797			
Total	142				

Supplemental Table 4 (continued).

(A) PD1 - Source of variation	df	MS	Pseudo-F	P-perm	Perm#
Sequence	1	14.467	3.6491	0.0624	9955
Depth	1	4.0982	1.0251	0.4757	9950
Geographic reg	1	5.8725	1.8332	0.2457	4349
Site(Geographic reg)	3	3.4354	1.3782	0.2163	9945
Residuals	33	2.4926			
Total	39				

(B) PD2 - Source of variation	df	MS	Pseudo-F	P-perm	Perm #
Sequence	2	21.598	5.5776	0.0034	9957
Depth	1	9.1842	1.5785	0.2661	9957
Geographic reg	1	0.2592	0.0602	0.9686	4349
Site(Geographic reg)	3	5.344	2.7883	0.0112*	9945
Residuals	44	1.9166			
Total	51				

(C) D - Source of variation	df	MS	Pseudo-F	P-perm	Perm #
Sequence	2	5.1439	1.4626	0.2376	9954
Depth	1	20.334	4.3356	0.0479	9952
Geographic reg	1	5.2435	1.4141	0.2939	4303
Site(Geographic reg)	3	4.5588	1.9513	0.0645	9932
Residuals	43	2.3362			
Total	50				

Supplemental Table 5. Canonical analysis of principal coordinates (CAP) of study factors on Exclusive data. (A) *A priori* analysis using shell growth region-aggregated data. (B) Post-hoc analysis using PD1 shell data. (C) Post-hoc analysis using PD2 shell data. (D) Post-hoc analysis using D-shell data. 1st SCC (δ_1^2) and 2nd SCC (δ_2^2) = the first and second squared correlation coefficient, which indicate the strength of the association between the multivariate data and the first and second canonical axis; 1st SCC *p* = the p-value associated with the test of the null hypothesis that the variation captured by the first canonical axis is not related to the differences in elemental composition between levels of a given study factor; Choice of *m* = the number of PCO axes chosen to maximize allocation success; Prop. G = the overall proportion of variation explained by the first *m* PCO axes; Trace statistic = a measure of the degree to which CAP is able to separate levels of a study factor; Trace statistic *p* = the p-value associated with the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference between study factor level centroids.

(A) <i>A priori</i> output	Depth	Geographic Region	Site	Growth Region
1 st SCC (δ_1^2)	0.2817	0.1209	0.5073	0.032
1 st SCC <i>p</i>	0.0001	0.0003	0.0001	0.27
2 nd SCC (δ_2^2)	N/A	N/A	0.1562	0.0157
Choice of <i>m</i>	3	3	3	2
Prop. G	3	1	1	0.8406
Trace statistic	0.28175	0.12091	0.7462	0.04768
Trace statistic <i>p</i>	0.0001	0.0003	0.0001	0.1423

(B) PD1 post-hoc output	Depth	Geographic Region	Site
1 st SCC (δ_1^2)	0.3037	0.0955	0.4882
1 st SCC <i>p</i>	0.0039	0.1587	0.0035
2 nd SCC (δ_2^2)	N/A	N/A	0.4463
Choice of <i>m</i>	3	2	2
Prop. G	1	0.8427	0.8427
Trace statistic	0.3037	0.09552	0.56583
Trace statistic <i>p</i>	0.0039	0.1587	0.0199

(C) PD2 post-hoc output	Depth	Geographic Region	Site
1 st SCC (δ_1^2)	0.3871	0.1517	0.7058
1 st SCC <i>p</i>	0.0001	0.0166	0.0001
2 nd SCC (δ_2^2)	N/A	N/A	0.3334
Choice of <i>m</i>	2	2	3
Prop. G	0.896	0.896	1
Trace statistic	0.38711	0.15169	1.25891
Trace statistic <i>p</i>	0.0001	0.0166	0.0001

Supplemental Table 5 (continued).

(D) D-shell post-hoc output	Depth	Geographic Region	Site
1 st SCC (δ_1^2)	0.3663	0.2238	0.5393
1 st SCC p	0.0001	0.0083	0.0002
2 nd SCC (δ_2^2)	N/A	N/A	0.4314
Choice of m	2	3	3
Prop. G	0.8202	1	1
Trace statistic	0.36634	0.22382	1.08307
Trace statistic p	0.0001	0.0083	0.0001

Supplemental Table 6. Effect size of individual factors for Exclusive data. Effect size is calculated as the percentage of variation attributed to between-group variation relative to total variation (between and within groups). The Type I SS analysis first accounts for variability associated with methods (Burn date, Sequence, Burn group), then factors in descending ecological hierarchical order. Depth is prioritized before other ecological study factors.

Source of variation	Estimate	Effect Size (%)
Sequence	0.18484	12.62
Depth	0.13086	9.28
Geographic reg	-0.14588	0.00
Site(Geographic reg)	0.43629	25.42
Sample number(Site(Geographic reg))	0.83919	39.61
Growth region	0.09781	7.10
<i>Among prodissoconch</i>	0.049991	3.76
<i>Between prodissoconch and diss.</i>	0.09211	6.71
Geographic reg x Growth region	0.75074	36.97
<i>Geographic reg x Among prodissoconch</i>	0.80554	38.63
<i>Geographic reg x Between pro. and diss.</i>	0.3776	22.78
Site(Geographic region) x Growth region	0.41227	24.37
<i>Site(Geographic reg) x Among prodissoconch</i>	0.6368	33.23
<i>Site(Geographic reg) x Between pro. and diss.</i>	0.23881	15.73
Residual	1.2797	50.00

Supplemental Table 7. Spearman rank correlations with CAP axes and overall vector lengths associated with elemental ratios for *Gigantidas childressi* Exclusive data with growth regions combined and separated. Vector length = a measure of the explanatory power of the elemental ratio considering both canonical axes, calculated as the sum of the squared canonical coefficients or the value of the canonical coefficient when CAP is one-dimensional. Positive and negative signs indicate the direction of the relationship with respect to the canonical axis for Depth (negative = left and generally deeper depths; positive = right and generally shallower depths) and Geographic Region (negative = left and generally associated with the WAM; positive = right and generally associated with the GOM). Single asterisks indicate a correlation (r) > 0.3. Double asterisks indicate a correlation (r) > 0.7.

Study factor	Elemental ratio (mmol:mol, X:Ca)	Vector length (PD1, PD2, D)	Vector length (PD1)	Vector length (PD2)	Vector length (D)
Depth	Cd:Ca	-0.08196	-0.25929	-0.4933*	+0.42824*
	Ba:Ca	+0.93367**	+0.95478**	+0.5838*	+0.95964**
	Sn:Ca	-0.02505	+0.19906	-0.59908*	+0.42805*
Geographic region	Cd:Ca	+0.26528	+0.36773*	-0.73508**	+0.75520**
	Ba:Ca	+0.63322*	+0.72045**	+0.27576	+0.63412*
	Sn:Ca	-0.33328*	+0.83133**	-0.77179**	+0.04163
Site	Cd:Ca	0.66934*	0.89274**	0.56167*	0.68479*
	Ba:Ca	0.87261**	0.92178**	0.86010**	0.97977**
	Sn:Ca	0.36311*	0.86271**	1.007**	0.54301
Growth region	Cd:Ca	0.85718**			
	Ba:Ca	0.97989**			
	Sn:Ca	0.84651**			

Supplemental Table 8. Classification success of cross-validation of *Gigantidas childressi*

Exclusive data. (A) two geographic regions (GOM and WAM), (B) eight sites (Brine Pool – BP, GB907, GB648, Veatch Canyon – VEC, New England Canyon – NE, Norfolk Canyon – NC, Mississippi Canyon 853 – MC853, Alaminos Canyon 645 – AC645), and (C) three growth regions (prodissoconch I – PD1, prodissoconch II – PD2, dissoconch – D).

(A) Geographic region

Orig. group	Classified group		Group N	% Correct
	GOM	WAM		
GOM	82	41	123	66.667
WAM	8	12	20	60

Total Correct: 94/143 (65.734%)

Total Incorrect: 49/143 (34.266%)

(B) Site

Orig. group	Classified group							Group N	% Correct
	BP	GB907	GB648	NC	MC853	AC645	NE		
BP	26	4	3	0	1	2	0	36	72.222
GB907	8	10	6	5	1	6	0	36	27.778
GB648	1	2	10	2	2	3	2	22	45.455
NC	0	0	2	6	1	2	1	12	50
MC853	2	1	2	2	9	4	0	20	45
AC645	0	2	1	3	3	0	0	9	0
NE	0	1	1	2	3	1	0	8	0

Total Correct: 61/143 (42.657%)

Total Incorrect: 82/143 (57.343%)

(C) Growth region

Orig. group	Classified group			Group N	% Correct
	PD1	PD2	D		
PD1	7	14	19	40	17.5
PD2	11	20	21	52	38.462
D	12	11	28	51	54.902

Total Correct: 55/143 (38.462%)

Total Incorrect: 88/143 (61.538%)

Supplemental Table 9. Permutational dispersion test (PERMDISP) on Exclusive data.

PERMDISP tested if within-group dispersion could have influenced PERMANOVA significance. F = F value; df1 = first degrees of freedom value, attributed to variance between groups; df2 = second degrees of freedom value, attributed to variance within groups; P-perm = p-value under permutation; Lib/Con/Unc/Insig = identifier for if the test was liberal (smaller group(s) has greater dispersion), conservative (larger group(s) has greater dispersion), uncertain (high number of groups with different dispersions obscures clear patterns), or insignificant at the 5% significance level. Bold values indicate significance at the 5% significance level.

Source of variation	F	df1	df2	P-perm	Lib/Con/Unc/Insig
Site (on Sample Num DAC)	1.0461	6	56	0.504	Insignificant
Site (no DAC)	3.2428	6	136	0.0075	Liberal
Sample Num	3.4289	62	80	0.5286	Insignificant

composition labeled by methods and study factors. (A) Ablation order (burn number), (B) Analytical session, (C) sequence, (D) Burn group, (E) Depth, (F) geographic region, (G) site, (H) growth region. The overlain circle and lines represent Pearson rank correlations of elemental ratios as a proportion of 1 (unitless, circle radius).

Supplemental Figure 2. Methodological factors (burn number and ablation sequence) regressed against depth in meters. (A) Subsample burn number plotted against depth (m). (B) Subsample ablation sequence plotted against depth (m). The black lines show the linear regression (depth = a * burn number *or* sequence + b). The coefficients of determination are shown (R^2) for both methodological factors. A positive slope indicates that subsamples from deeper depths were generally ablated later.

Supplemental Figure 3. Canonical analysis of principal coordinates (CAP) of Exclusive shell composition for *G. childressi* shell analyzed against depth as a continuous variable for combined growth regions. The canonical axis represents the first and only constrained component and the percentage of variation explained by the linear combination of selected elemental ratios. The Depth axis represents the depth of each study site. BP, Brine Pool; GB907, Garden Banks 907; GB648, Garden Banks 648; VEC, Veatch Canyon; NE, New England Seep; NC, Norfolk Canyon; MC853, Mississippi Canyon 853; AC645, Alaminos Canyon 645.

Supplemental Figure 4. Canonical analysis of principal coordinates (CAP) of Exclusive shell composition for *G. childressi* shell analyzed against depth as a continuous variable for individual growth regions. (A) PD1 shell, (B) PD2 shell, (C) D shell. The canonical axis represents the first and only constrained component and the percentage of variation explained by the linear combination of selected elemental ratios. The Depth axis represents the depth of each study site. BP, Brine Pool; GB907, Garden Banks 907; GB648, Garden Banks 648; VEC, Veatch

Canyon; NE, New England Seep; NC, Norfolk Canyon; MC853, Mississippi Canyon 853;
AC645, Alaminos Canyon 645.

Supplemental Figure 5. Canonical analysis of principal coordinates (CAP) of Exclusive TEFs for *G. childressi* shell to assess differences between geographic regions for combined growth regions. The canonical axis represents the first and only constrained component and the percentage of variation explained by the linear combination of selected elemental ratios. GOM, Gulf of Mexico; WAM, West Atlantic Margin.

Supplemental Figure 6. Log ratios of magnesium, strontium, and barium to calcium (mmol:mol) used to discriminate larval and settled shells of *G. childressi* for Exclusive data. Boxplots show the median (horizontal bar), 25th percentile, and 75th percentile of the transformed and normalized dataset; whiskers show minimum and maximum values. Boxplots show data for each study factor: (A) values among growth regions: PD1, prodissoconch I; PD2, prodissoconch II; D, dissoconch. (B) Values among sites: BP, Brine Pool; GB907, Garden Banks 907; GB648, Garden Banks 648; VEC, Veatch Canyon; NE, New England Seep; NC, Norfolk Canyon; MC853, Mississippi Canyon 853; AC645, Alaminos Canyon 645. (C) Values among geographic regions: GOM, Gulf of Mexico; WAM, West Atlantic Margin.

Supplemental Figure 7. Canonical analysis of principal coordinates (CAP) of Exclusive TEFs for *G. childressi* shell to assess differences between geographic regions for individual growth regions. (A) PD2 and (B) D shell. The canonical axis represents the first and only constrained component and the percentage of variation explained by the linear combination of selected elemental ratios. GOM, Gulf of Mexico; WAM, West Atlantic Margin.

Supplemental Figure 8. Canonical analysis of principal coordinates (CAP) of Exclusive TEFs for *G. childressi* shell to assess differences between study sites for combined growth regions. Axes represent the first and second constrained component and the percentage of variation explained by the linear combination of selected elemental ratios. The overlain circle and lines represent spearman rank correlations of elemental ratios as a proportion of 1 (unitless, circle radius). BP, Brine Pool; GB907, Garden Banks 907; GB648, Garden Banks 648; VEC, Veatch Canyon; NE, New England Seep; NC, Norfolk Canyon; MC853, Mississippi Canyon 853; AC645, Alaminos Canyon 645.

Supplemental Figure 9. Canonical analysis of principal coordinates (CAP) of Exclusive TEFs for *G. childressi* shell to assess differences between study sites for individual growth regions. (A) PD1 shell, (B) PD2 shell, (C) D shell. Axes represent the first and second constrained component and the percentage of variation explained by the linear combination of selected elemental ratios. The overlain circle and lines represent spearman rank correlations of

elemental ratios as a proportion of 1 (unitless, circle radius). BP, Brine Pool; GB907, Garden Banks 907; GB648, Garden Banks 648; VEC, Veatch Canyon; NE, New England Seep; NC, Norfolk Canyon; MC853, Mississippi Canyon 853; AC645, Alaminos Canyon 645.